

Fertilizer management—biological N

Blue-green algae (BGA) as a partial N substitute for rainfed lowland rice

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BGA has a photo-autotrophic N-fixing system and may be used as partial substitute for N fertilizer in rice.

We conducted a 4-yr field experiment to evaluate the utility of BGA in rainfed lowland rice. JR3-756, Usha, and Asha rice varieties were the test crops.

Soil was red-yellow clay loam with pH 7.00, 1.7% organic matter, CEC 33.8 meq/100 g soil, 0.08% total N, 5 ppm available P (Olsen), and 0.07 meq exchangeable K/100 g soil. P and K were applied basally at 26 kg P and 33 kg K/ha. Treatments (see table) were in a random block design with

four replications. N was applied in three splits (25% basal, 50% at tillering, and 25% at panicle initiation).

Indigenous BGA were not found in any plot. Grain yield and net profit

increased with each incremental level of N alone (see table). Inoculation of 10 kg BGA algal crust/ha gave a grain yield and net profit nearly equivalent to that with 25 kg N/ha. Net profit increased when BGA was supplemented with 25 kg N/ha. □

Utility of BGA inoculation of rainfed lowland rice. Raipur, MP, India.

Treatment	Grain yield ^a (tha)					Gross return ^b (US\$)	Cost of treatment (US\$)	Net profit (US\$)
	1978	1979	1980	1981	Mean			
Control (no N)	1.0	3.0	2.7	2.0	2.2	218.00	0.00	218.00
25 kg N/ha as urea	1.2	3.5	3.4	2.5	2.7	265.00	9.25	255.75
50 kg N as urea	1.4	4.4	3.8	2.8	3.1	310.00	18.50	291.50
75 kg N as urea	1.5	4.7	4.2	3.2	3.4	339.00	27.75	311.25
10 kg BGA/ha, algal crust inoculated	1.2	3.6	3.3	2.2	2.6	256.00	0.67	255.33
10 kg BGA/ha, algal crust inoculated + 25 kg N/ha	1.3	3.7	3.5	2.4	2.8	275.00	9.92	265.08
LSD (0.05)	0.3	0.6	0.4	0.3				
CV (%)	14	11	7	7				

^aVarieties were JR3-756 for 1978, Ucha for 1979 and 1980, Asha for 1981. ^bRates: rice \$100/t, N \$0.37/kg, BGA \$0.67/10 kg.

Decapitating young *Sesbania rostrata* plants to increase biomass production and nitrogen fixation

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A green manure crop for intensive rice production systems should produce high biomass within a very short fallow. Under optimal conditions, *Sesbania rostrata* has the capacity to produce 5.6 t dry matter with 100 kg N content/ha in 50 d.

Apical dominance in dicotyledonous plants inhibits the growth of axillary buds. Removal of apical dominance would permit more rapid growth of axillary buds, which could result in higher biomass production. Increased stem nodulation has been achieved in *S. rostrata* under laboratory conditions,

by injecting an *Azorhizobial* suspension into the vascular system of the plant.

We examined whether growth and stem nodulation could be improved by decapitating young *Sesbania* plants prior to stem inoculation. The experiment was conducted mid-Jun to mid-Aug in the intermediate zone of Sri Lanka (12.5 h daylength). Surface-sterilized *Sesbania* seeds were planted

in 3-m² plots, in three rows 10 cm apart, at 20 seeds/row.

Treatments (see table) were in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Plots were flooded 35 d after seeding (DAS), when the plants were 30 cm tall. Decapitation and stem inoculation were done 46 DAS, when plants were 50 cm tall.

Stem inoculation was done by

Effect of decapitation and stem inoculation on growth and N₂ fixation in *S. rostrata*.^a

Treatment	Dry weight/plant (g)	Nodule dry weight/plant (g)	ARA (μmol/h)	N yield/plant (mg)
Control - no decapitation, no stem inoculation	4.280 c	0.1196 b	10.8 c	45.3 b
Inoculation without decapitation	6.217 b (45)	0.1898 ab (59)	21.9 b (103)	81.6 ab (80)
Decapitation without inoculation	7.543 b (76)	0.2039 ab (70)	24.7 b (129)	96.9 ab (114)
Decapitation and inoculation	9.287 a (116)	0.3290 a (175)	49.7 a (360)	128.5 a (184)

^a Figures in parentheses are 5% increase over control. Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.